

Antibody Characterization Report for Excitatory amino acid transporter 1 (EAAT1)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Excitatory amino acid transporter 1

Protein name (short): EAAT1

Alternative protein names: Sodium-dependent glutamate/aspartate transporter 1, GLAST-1, Solute carrier family 1 member 3

Gene name: *SLC1A3*

Uniprot: P43003

This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Excitatory amino acid transporter 1 (EAAT1). We used an antibody characterization pipeline¹ based on knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for EAAT1 by immunoblot (Western blot). HCT116 and HAP1 *SLC1A3* KO cells are available at RESOLUTE and Horizon Discovery, respectively, and were used for screening antibodies.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

- 1 Laflamme, C. *et al.* Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife* **8**, doi:10.7554/eLife.48363 (2019).

Table 1: Summary of the EAAT1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)
Thermo	PA5-19709	VJ3101248	AB_10982702	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1.00
Thermo	PA5-72895	VJ3101524A	AB_2718749	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1.00
Bio-Techne	MAB6048	CMNK012001	AB_2885147	monoclonal	482420	Mouse	0.50
MilliporeSigma	MABN794	3389915	AB_2811303	monoclonal	8C11.1	Mouse	1.00
Proteintech	20785-1-AP	not provided	AB_2878738	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.36
Abcam	ab176557	GR137919-3	AB_2885100	recombinant-mono	EPR12685	rabbit	0.08
Abcam	ab181036	GR3258023-6	AB_2885103	recombinant-mono	EPR20556	rabbit	0.49
Abcam	ab181661	GR3371723-2	AB_2885104	monoclonal	-	mouse	1.00
Abcam	ab41751	GR3368493-1	AB_955879	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.90

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype	Comment
RESOLUTE	CE00EH-8	-	HCT116	WT	-
RESOLUTE	CE058N-A	-	HCT116	<i>SLC1A3</i> KO ¹	see footnote
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT	-
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC001578c011	CVCL_TL84	HAP1	<i>SLC1A3</i> KO	-

¹ Please contact RESOLUTE (contact@re-solute.eu) to obtain this KO cell line.

Figure 1: Analysis of EAAT1 antibodies by immunoblot.

A) Lysates of HCT116 and HAP1 (WT or *SLC1A3* KO) were prepared and 100 µg of protein were processed for immunoblot with the indicated EAAT1 antibodies. Antibody dilution used is 1/1000 for all tested antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used was 1/1000. H116 = HCT116. Expected band size: ~60 kDa.

B) Lysates of the indicated cell lines (HAP1, HCT116, HEK293, HeLa, A549, U2OS) were prepared and 25 µg of protein were processed for immunoblot with ab176557 at a dilution of 1/200. Two different exposures are depicted. exp.=exposure, H116 = HCT116

Figure 1: EAAT1 antibody screening by immunoblot

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All EAAT1 antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520).

Cell culture

HAP1 and HCT116 were cultured in DMEM high-glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% bovine calf serum (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30072.03), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Immunoblot

Both HAP1 and HCT116 WT and *SLC1A3* KO cells, as well as HEK293, HeLa, A549 and U2OS, were collected in RIPA buffer (50 mM Tris pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 1.0 mM EDTA, 1% Triton X-100, 0.5% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~115,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and immunoblot.

Immunoblots for antibody screening were performed with large 4-15% gradient polyacrylamide gels and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. The cell line panel was performed with a straight 8% polyacrylamide gel. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual immunoblot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% bovine serum albumin in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were then incubated with ECL from Pierce (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with HyBlot CL autoradiography films from Denville (cat. number 1159T41).